

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE ANALGESIC EFFICACY OF
ULTRASOUND-GUIDED TRANSVERSUS ABDOMINIS PLANE BLOCK
AND DIRECT INFILTRATION OF BUPIVACAINE INTO THE SURGICAL
INCISION IN LOWER ABDOMINAL GYNECOLOGICAL SURGERIES

Dr. Bushra Khatoon^{*1}, Dr. M. Ashraf Zia²

^{*1}Post Graduate Resident Department of Anesthesia, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore Pakistan

²Professor and Head of Anesthesia Department, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore Pakistan

^{*1}bkhatoon1996@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18159544>

Keywords

Analgesia; Bupivacaine; Local Anesthetics; Nerve Block; Pain Management; Postoperative Pain; Transversus Abdominis Plane Block;

Article History

Received: 20 March 2025

Accepted: 02 May 2025

Published: 18 May 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Bushra Khatoon

Abstract

Objective: To evaluate and compare the analgesic effectiveness of ultrasound-guided transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block against the direct infiltration of bupivacaine in lower abdominal gynecological surgeries.

Study Design: A randomized controlled trial

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Anesthesia, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, for six months from 1-08-2024 till 31-01-2025.

Methodology: A total of 60 female patients aged 20–60 years, ASA I–III, and scheduled for lower abdominal gynecological surgery under general anesthesia, were randomly divided into two equal groups. The outcomes assessed were time to first rescue analgesia, 24-hour pain scores (VAS), and 24-hour opioid consumption, done postoperatively. As a result of non-normal data distribution, non-parametric tests were used, and $p \leq 0.05$ was taken as statistically significant in SPSS version 27.0.

Results: The TAP block extended the time to first rescue analgesia significantly (median 367.0 min [IQR 36.75]) as compared to the infiltration group (250.5 min [IQR 46.50]) ($p < 0.001$). The pain scores after 24 hours were less in the TAP group (median 3.0 [IQR 1.00]) than in the infiltration group (5.9 [IQR 1.15]) ($p < 0.001$). Opioid consumption in the first 24 hours was significantly less in the TAP group (94.5 mg [IQR 26.50]) than in the infiltration group (198.0 mg [IQR 26.25]) ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The TAP block showed analgesic effects that were significantly better than infiltration as indicated by the much longer time to first rescue analgesia, lower pain scores after 24 hours, and less opioid intake (all $p < 0.001$).

INTRODUCTION

Surgeries in the gynecological field that involve the lower abdomen usually come with a lot of postoperative pain, which can delay the recovery process and keep the patients in the hospital for a longer time. Thus, the effective analgesia during the

postoperative period is very important to increase the patient's comfort, cut down on the opioid intake, and decrease the side effects. Out of the different types of regional analgesia methods, the ultrasound-guided TAP block has been recognized in terms of its

effectiveness in cutting down the pain after surgery by blocking the anterior abdominal wall-feeding nerves (1). TAP block is very much appreciated for its effect of less opioid need and also being fairly safe compared to the use of systemic analgesics (2). On the contrary, the direct bupivacaine infiltration into the incision site is a less complicated method but still very effective for pain management, as it leads to numbness in the localized area and thus cuts off peripheral nociceptive input (3).

Research conducted across the globe indicates that regional anesthesia methods such as TAP blocks have gained acceptance in the field of gynecological surgeries, owing to the longer duration of analgesia in some cases and offering better relief from pain during mobilization (2,4). The findings of meta-analyses suggest that TAP block and local infiltration show comparable short-term analgesic efficacy; however, the former is associated with longer-lasting effects (5). In Pakistan, the management of pain after gynecological surgery remains a difficult task; the use of opioids is widespread but is accompanied by a high prevalence of side effects such as nausea, which can affect up to 33% of patients, leading to a need for the incorporation of multimodal and regional analgesia(3,6). Around 40-50% of the individuals who have undergone abdominal surgeries related to gynecology suffer from moderate to severe pain during the postoperative period unless optimized multimodal analgesia is applied (1).

The comparison of the two analgesic methods—ultrasound-assisted TAP block and local bupivacaine injection—brings along the issue of integrating all of the above into a pain management strategy that is evidence-based, safe, effective, and low-cost regionally. TAP block is more complicated since it requires ultrasound expertise and availability, whereas local infiltration is easier but might give less time of pain relief. Relatively distinguishing their effectiveness will help to develop anesthetic protocols that will enhance the postoperative recovery for gynecological surgery patients.

Methodology:

This study was a randomized controlled trial that was conducted in the Department of Anesthesia, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, over a span of six months (from 1-08-2024 till 31-01-2025) after receiving the approval of the Institutional Ethical Review Board. The

number of subjects consisted of 60 female patients who were going to have lower abdominal gynecological surgeries under general anesthesia, and they were selected through simple random sampling.

Inclusion criteria: Women between the ages of 20 and 60 years with ASA physical status I-III were admitted

Exclusion criteria: Patients with liver, kidney problems, bleeding disorders, or known allergy to bupivacaine were excluded.

The sample size was determined by the WHO calculator, depending on a reported average pain score of 3.01 ± 2.55 with ultrasound-guided TAP block and 6.04 ± 2.74 with local infiltration, setting the power of the study at 90% and confidence level at 95%(7).

After taking informed written consent, demographic and clinical data such as age, height, weight, BMI, ASA status, type of surgery, history of smoking, hypertension, and diabetes were recorded. The same general anesthesia was given, and the operative time, along with blood loss during surgery, was noted.

Using the lottery method, participants were randomly assigned to two equal groups. Group A received 25 mg of 0.5% bupivacaine administered bilaterally through ultrasound guidance of the transversus abdominis plane. Aseptic conditions were maintained while a high-frequency ultrasound probe was placed transversely between the iliac crest and costal margin, and a 22-gauge echogenic needle was advanced in-plane. After seeing the tip of the needle, 2 mL of local anesthetic was injected for hydro-dissection to confirm correct placement, then the remaining volume diluted to a concentration of 0.125% was instilled. In Group B, local infiltration was done by injecting 10 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine directly into the surgical incision after skin closure and before reversal from anesthesia. Patients were monitored postoperatively in the recovery area, and the time to first rescue analgesia, which was defined as a pain score greater than 4 on the visual analogue scale, was recorded in minutes. Pain scores after 24 hours and total opioid consumption, using tramadol 1 mg/kg as rescue analgesia, were also documented according to the operational definitions.

The assessment of normality performed with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests revealed that the demographic and perioperative

variables, age, BMI, operative time, and intraoperative blood loss showed nonsignificant p-values ($p > 0.05$) and thus were normally distributed. On the contrary, the postoperative variables show that non-normality was evidenced, and, specifically, the time of first rescue analgesia, the pain score at 24 hours, and the 24-hour opioid consumption were subjected to normality testing, which resulted in significant p-values ($p < 0.05$), hence concluding that their distributions are non-normal.

The descriptive statistics, whereby normally distributed variables were reported as mean \pm Standard Deviation (SD) while non-normally distributed variables were reported as median with interquartile range. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to conduct group comparisons for postoperative outcomes that indicated non-normal distribution, p value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Figure 1: Patient flow diagram

Results:

The mean age of the study sample was 38.76 ± 7.27 years, which was close to the mean age of participants in the Infiltration group (39.03 ± 7.45 years) and the TAP group (38.49 ± 7.20 years). Participants in the Infiltration group had an average BMI of 26.92 ± 3.18 kg/m², compared to the TAP group average of 27.05 ± 3.46 kg/m², resulting in an overall average BMI of 26.98 ± 3.30 kg/m². The infiltration group had a mean duration of surgery of

89.43 ± 14.13 minutes, while patients in the TAP group had a mean of 92.67 ± 15.81 minutes, thus

making a total average of 91.05 ± 14.96 minutes. Infiltration group intraoperative blood loss was recorded at 260.20 ± 86.08 ml and TAP at 259.30 ± 96.73 ml, which combined made the mean blood loss of 259.75 ± 90.78 ml.

Table I: Baseline demographic and perioperative characteristics of the TAP block(n=30) vs. infiltration groups (n=30)

Variable	Infiltration (n = 30)	TAP (n = 30)	Total (n = 60)
Age (years)	39.033 ± 7.4528	38.487 ± 7.1958	38.760 ± 7.2683
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.920 ± 3.1796	27.047 ± 3.4639	26.983 ± 3.2971
Operative time (min)	89.43 ± 14.127	92.67 ± 15.812	91.05 ± 14.955
Intraoperative blood loss (ml)	260.20 ± 86.082	259.30 ± 96.730	259.75 ± 90.783

The time to first rescue analgesia varied widely between the two groups, being much longer in the TAP group (367.0 minutes, IQR 35.5) than in the infiltration group (250.5 minutes, IQR 45.0). The combined interquartile range (IQR) was 312.0 minutes (IQR 116.5). The 24-hour pain score was higher in the TAP group (median 3.0, IQR 1.0) than in the infiltration group (median 5.9, IQR 1.1),

while the total sample population exhibited a median pain score of 4.6 (IQR 2.9). Additionally, the TAP group had a significantly lower opioid consumption over 24 hours (median 94.5 mg, IQR 26.0) than the infiltration group (198.0 mg, IQR 25.5), leading to a combined median of 142.0 mg (IQR 103.5).

Table II: Median (IQR) postoperative analgesic outcomes in TAP block(n=30) vs. infiltration groups (n=30)

Variable	TAP (Median, IQR)	Infiltration (Median, IQR)	Total (Median, IQR)
Time to first rescue analgesia (min)	367.0 (35.5)	250.5 (45.0)	312.0 (116.5)
Pain score at 24 hours (VAS)	3.0 (1.0)	5.9 (1.1)	4.6 (2.9)
Opioid consumption in 24 hours (mg)	94.5 (26.0)	198.0 (25.5)	142.0 (103.5)

The categorical variable distributions were similar in both groups. In the ASA class, the Infiltration and TAP groups both had the same distribution, with Class I having 10 (33.3%), Class II having 15 (50.0%), and Class III having 5 (16.7%). Smoking status revealed that the Infiltration group consisted of 17 (56.7%) non-smokers and 13 (43.3%) smokers,

while the TAP group had 20 (66.7%) non-smokers and 10 (33.3%) smokers. Patients with hypertension were 12 (40.0%) in the Infiltration group and 9 (30.0%) in the TAP group; non-hypertensive patients were 18 (60.0%) and 21 (70.0%), respectively. Diabetes affected 11 (36.7%) of the Infiltration group and 5 (16.7%) of the TAP group, while non-diabetics were 19 (63.3%) and 25 (83.3%), respectively.

Table III: Categorical variables compared between TAP block(n=30) vs. infiltration groups (n=30)

Variable	Category	Infiltration (n=30)	TAP (n=30)
ASA Class	I	10 (33.3%)	10 (33.3%)
	II	15 (50.0%)	15 (50.0%)
	III	5 (16.7%)	5 (16.7%)
Smoking	No	17 (56.7%)	20 (66.7%)
	Yes	13 (43.3%)	10 (33.3%)
Hypertension	No	18 (60.0%)	21 (70.0%)
	Yes	12 (40.0%)	9 (30.0%)
Diabetes	No	19 (63.3%)	25 (83.3%)
	Yes	11 (36.7%)	5 (16.7%)

The median time to first rescue analgesia in the TAP group was 367.0 minutes (IQR 36.75) and in the infiltration group 250.5 minutes (IQR 46.50) ($p < 0.001$). The 24-hour pain score has a median of 3.0 (IQR 1.00) for TAP and 5.9 (IQR 1.15) for

infiltration ($p < 0.001$). Opioid consumption in 24 hours was 94.5 mg (IQR 26.50) in the TAP group and 198.0 mg (IQR 26.25) in the infiltration group ($p < 0.001$).

Table IV: Postoperative outcomes between TAP block(n=30) vs. infiltration groups (n=30) with corresponding p-values.

Variable	Group	Median (IQR)	p-value*
Time to first rescue analgesia (min)	TAP	367.0 (36.75)	<0.001
	Infiltration	250.5 (46.50)	
Pain score at 24 hours (VAS)	TAP	3.0 (1.00)	<0.001
	Infiltration	5.9 (1.15)	
Opioid consumption in 24 hours (mg)	TAP	94.5 (26.50)	<0.001
	Infiltration	198.0 (26.25)	

Discussion:

Based on the outcomes of this research, it can be concluded that the application of the transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block constituted a significant step forward in pain relief over local infiltration of the wound for postoperative pain management in the case of lower abdominal gynecological surgeries(8,9). The time to first rescue analgesia in the TAP group (367.0 mins) was noticeably longer than that of the infiltration group (250.5 mins), and the amount of opioid taken (94.5 mg vs. 198.0 mg) was also considerably reduced, thus confirming recent literature assertions of TAP block as a reliable part of multimodal analgesia in surgery of the abdomen. Randomized controlled trials done in the past few years have also indicated that ultrasound-guided TAP blocks dramatically decrease postoperative pain and cut down on opioid consumption for different gynecological and abdominal procedures. Works published after 2020, including those in cesarean section populations, have indicated prolonged analgesia and reduced opioid consumption in TAP block patients, thus closely matching the findings of the study at hand(10,11). Currently, technology and research have come a long way in developed countries, as the majority of the evidence produced is in favor of TAP blocks as the best choice to manage pain. Nevertheless, some

reports do not deny the sharpness of the distinctions in support of TAP blocks, as when the authors of a comparative randomized trial conducted in 2021 in gynecologic surgeries reported that the local infiltration analgesia did not tap blocks beyond the immediate postoperative period(12). The differences in studies might be due to the timing of blocks, anesthetic volumes, concentrations, and the components of multimodal analgesia. Also, adopting ultrasound guidance and giving the TAP block before surgical incision in this research may have ensured block success, hence contributing to the more extensive analgesic benefits that were noticed(13,14).

Demographic and intraoperative characteristics comparability between both groups, such as operative time, intraoperative blood loss, age, and BMI, indicates that there are balanced baseline profiles, which minimizes the impact of confounding factors on postoperative pain outcomes. This consistency increases the confidence that the analgesic endpoints' differences are due to the analgesic techniques and not patient- or procedure-related variability.

The differences are the statistically significant ones in all major postoperative analgesic outcomes, such as time to first rescue analgesia, 24-hour pain scores, and opioid consumption (all $p < 0.001$), which are

not only statistically but also clinically relevant. The remarkably lower median pain score in the TAP group (3.0 vs. 5.9) indicates not only that there was a lesser need for opioids but also that there was a better subjective pain control(15,16). It is further recommended that the TAP block should be integrated into ERAS pathways for gynecologic surgery, where opioid use reduction and early postoperative comfort performance optimization remain the primary objectives (17,18).

Moreover, an observation can be made regarding the similarity in blood loss and duration of surgery between the two groups, which indicates that none of the analgesic techniques negatively affected intraoperative surgical conditions. The finding, thus, adds to the safety profile of TAP block and its acceptability for routine gynecological surgical practice(19,20).

This research presents a variety of strengths, such as comparable baseline features, ultrasound-assisted block administration, and an extensive comparative study of several analgesic outcomes. The singular investigation of lower abdominal gynecological surgeries provides specificity and clinical significance to the outcomes.

The single-center design may restrict its application to other settings, and the lack of long-term follow-up limits the comprehension of the prolonged analgesic effects or the development of chronic pain. Furthermore, opioid-free analgesic use during the study was not reported in detail, and this could have affected postoperative pain scores. Besides, no explanation was given regarding the differences in local anesthetic volumes or concentrations, and outcomes like patient satisfaction or functional recovery were not evaluated.

Conclusion:

The current study presents important evidence in favor of the use of ultrasound-guided TAP block as an effective analgesic method in lower abdominal gynecological surgeries. The block considerably delays the time to first rescue analgesia, decreases opioid consumption, and results in lower pain scores in comparison with local bupivacaine infiltration. The findings underscore the importance of the TAP block being part of the combination analgesic regimens. It is recommended that future multicenter

randomized trials with standardized anesthetic protocols and longer follow-ups be conducted to further confirm these findings and influence clinical practice.

REFERENCES:

1. Ismail S, Mistry AA, Siddiqui AS, Aziz A, Zuberi NF. The analgesic efficacy of ultrasound-guided transversus abdominis plane block vs. local anesthetic infiltration technique in major gynecologic surgery: a randomized controlled trial. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol* 2022;39(4):557-563.
http://doi.org/10.4103/joacp.joacp_254_21
2. Amin MN, Bhattacharjee R, Lisa SF, Akhter S. Postoperative pain management in gynecologic laparoscopic surgeries. *Int J Res Med Sci* 2025;13(1):102-106.
<http://doi.org/10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20244670>
3. Shahid N, Rashid AM, Khan RA. Effectiveness of port site bupivacaine infiltration in postoperative pain reduction after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a randomized controlled trial from a tertiary care hospital. *Prof Med J* 2024;31(02):165-170.
<http://doi.org/10.29309/tpmj/2024.31.02.7952>
4. El Hachem L, Small E, Chung P, Moshier EL, Friedman K, Fenske SS, et al. Randomized controlled double-blind trial of transversus abdominis plane block versus trocar site infiltration in gynecologic laparoscopy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2015;212(2):182.e1-9.
<http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2014.07.039>
5. Ahmad A, Arif A, Ataulah A, Muhammad F, Khan MA. Intraoperative local bupivacaine wound infiltration versus traditional systematic analgesia: a comparison in term of post-operative pain. *Biol Clin Sci Res J* 2024;2024(1):1281.
<http://doi.org/10.54112/bcsrj.v2024i1.1281>

6. Cong N, Guo YH, Xue FS. Letter to the Editor: Postoperative pain control and opioid use with transversus abdominis plane block and scheduled multimodal pain management in patients undergoing cesarean section. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 2025;169(2):859-860. <http://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.17007>
7. Ali L, Waseem M, Iqbal A. Comparison of analgesic efficacy of transversus abdominis plane block with conventional local anesthetic wound infiltration. *Pak Armed Forces Med J* 2018;68(5):1106-1110.
8. Manoharan MM, Gnanadesikan U, Elavarasan K, Nahendran K. Efficacy of transversus abdominis plane block for postoperative analgesia in different lower abdominal surgeries in a tertiary care hospital-Chengalpattu District. *Anesth Pain Med (Tehran)* 2023;13(2):e134864. <http://doi.org/10.5812/aapm-134864>
9. Otake A, Sasamoto N, Sato N, Kumasaka R, Yamamoto Y, Adachi K. Comparative study of postoperative analgesic effects of intraoperative levobupivacaine local infiltration anesthesia and transversus abdominis plane block following gynecologic laparoscopy. *Gynecol Minim Invasive Ther* 2022;11(4):231-237. http://doi.org/10.4103/gmit.gmit_129_21
10. Habib AS, Nedeljkovic SS, Horn JL, Smiley RM, Kett AG, Vallejo MC, et al. Randomized trial of transversus abdominis plane block with liposomal bupivacaine after cesarean delivery with or without intrathecal morphine. *J Clin Anesth* 2021;75:110527. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinane.2021.110527>
11. Innamorato MA, Vittori A, Natoli S, Perna P, Farinelli I, Petrucci E, et al. Bilateral transversus abdominis plane (TAP) block reduces pain and the need for additional analgesics after elective cesarean section under opioid-free spinal anesthesia: findings from a randomized clinical trial. *J Anesth Analg Crit Care* 2023;3(1):20. <http://doi.org/10.1186/s44158-023-00106-6>
12. Geng Z, Bi H, Zhang D, Xiao C, Song H, Feng Y, et al. The impact of multimodal analgesia based enhanced recovery protocol on quality of recovery after laparoscopic gynecological surgery: a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Anesthesiol* 2021;21(1):179. <http://doi.org/10.1186/s12871-021-01399-2>
13. Kahveci M, Abut FYÇ, Erdem G. Impact of ultrasonography-guided transversus abdominis plane block and local anesthetic infiltration in the surgical field on postoperative analgesic requirements for laparoscopic cholecystectomy procedures. *Istanbul Med J* 2024;25(4):269-273. <http://doi.org/10.4274/imj.2024.96020>
14. Yoon JP, Kim HY, Jung J, Lee JM, Park S, Byeon GJ. Analgesic effect of ultrasound-guided transversus abdominis plane block with or without rectus sheath block in laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a randomized, controlled trial. *Research Square* 2023. [Preprint]. <http://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3694080/v1>
15. Zhao Y, Zhang HY, Yuan ZY, Han Y, Chen YR, Liu QL, et al. Analgesic efficacy of postoperative bilateral, ultrasound-guided, posterior transversus abdominis plane block for laparoscopic colorectal cancer surgery: a randomized, prospective, controlled study. *BMC Anesthesiol* 2021;21(1):107. <http://doi.org/10.1186/s12871-021-01317-6>
16. He J, Qin S, Wang Y, Ye Q, Wang P, Zhang Y, et al. Rescue analgesia with a transversus abdominis plane block alleviates moderate-to-severe pain and improves oxygenation after abdominal surgery: a randomized controlled trial. *Front Pain Res (Lausanne)* 2024;5:1454665. <http://doi.org/10.3389/fpain.2024.1454665>
17. Geng Z, Wang B, Zhang Y, Yan X, Hu J, Cui R, et al. Preemptive multimodal analgesia for gynecologic oncology patients undergoing laparotomy: a randomized controlled trial. *Front Med (Lausanne)* 2024;11:1427548. <http://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1427548>

18. Wong J, Lim S, Rasugu D, Broach A, Song A, Sobolewski C. The impact of transversus abdominus plane (TAP) blocks for total laparoscopic hysterectomy on postoperative pain and recovery time: a retrospective analysis. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2024;230(4):S1244. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2024.02.261>
19. Zhang L, Jia Z, Gao T, Wang Y, Zhao Y, Li J, et al. A randomized controlled trial evaluating the effects of transversus abdominis plane block with compound lidocaine hydrochloride injection on postoperative pain and opioid consumption and gastrointestinal motility in patients undergoing gynecological laparoscopy. *Front Mol Neurosci* 2023;16:967917. <http://doi.org/10.3389/fnmol.2023.967917>
20. Sethi D, Garg G. Analgesic efficacy of ultrasound-guided transversus abdominis plane block for laparoscopic gynecological surgery: a randomized controlled trial. *Anesth Pain Med (Seoul)* 2022;17(1):67-74. <http://doi.org/10.17085/apm.21030>

